

VALUE OF DEVELOPING MEDIA LITERACY, MEDIA EDUCATION, INFORMATION CULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article due to the importance of developing media literacy, media education, information culture, development of information culture, ensuring citizens' media and information literacy (mas), the role of multimedia in increasing the level of effectiveness of the educational process among students is discussed in this article. and media literacy is discussed. Also, attention is paid to the issues of modern media and information literacy, the culture of using the internet and social networks, knowledge of information culture, psychological, regulatory, educational, ideological, reporting, diagnosing, perspective-setting tasks.*

Key words: *media and information literacy, new resources, media competence, educational process, new approach, multimedia lessons, development of media education*

INTRODUCTION:

The development of techniques and technologies during the last twenty years has led to an incomparable expansion of the media, information sources and information suppliers (libraries, archives, the Internet, etc.) and has made it possible for citizens to use and exchange its huge volume. As a result, citizens have the opportunity to assess whether this information is from reliable sources, to fully exercise their rights to freely express their opinion. That is why the urgent issue of ensuring citizens' media and information literacy (MIL) is put on the agenda.

According to Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, "Everyone has the right to freedom of belief and the freedom to express it; this right includes the freedom to hold one's beliefs without hindrance and to seek, receive and impart information and ideas through any media regardless of frontiers."

Media and other information services (libraries, archives, and the Internet) help people make decisions based on the abundance of information available around the world. In addition, they are a necessary tool by which society can learn the truth about itself, support communication with the population, and thereby move towards the goal in unison with it.

MIL is also a basic human right in the world of digitized information and digital technologies, which helps to increase the social activity of all peoples.

Media and other information services (libraries, archives, and the Internet) are recognized as important tools for people's decision-making in all regions, assuming completeness of information. In addition, they play the role of a valid tool for the government to know information about its activities, support communication with the population, and thereby move towards the set goals.

MAIN PART:

Mass communication and information channels have a great influence on the acquisition of knowledge throughout a person's life, therefore, not only future journalists, but also all citizens should learn how media and other information services (libraries, archives, Internet, etc.) work and it is necessary to know how to evaluate them correctly. The task of media and information literacy is to deliver this knowledge to users.

Today, the information society presents many problems to modern universities. The Internet and modern technologies not only filled the lack of information, prevented excessive time consumption and became a serious competitor of traditional educational norms. Teachers and students are constantly forced to look for new resources to improve their media competence. The teacher has the task of becoming a "guide" and a consultant in the world of information for students. Today, the student simultaneously works as a consumer of information content, information technologies, and as an author, creator of media products. Students' access to the modern information space often happens by itself and does not require much pedagogical support. For example, teaching students the ethical standards of communication, effective search and selection of safe information on the Internet, etc., seems relevant.

Development of students' media literacy should be considered as an important independent educational task in a modern university. Development of media and information skills in students requires advanced media competence. Teachers actively use a multimedia projector in the auditorium (nowadays lectures are rarely given without a presentation), video materials, and an interactive whiteboard. Some teachers have created a social page to communicate and post updates for students. Members of the online community use it for professional development. As a result of media education, media literacy is not limited to students' mastery of modern information technologies or development of critical information analysis skills. A broader view of the concept of media education is required.

In the efficient and quick use of information, the student can determine the type of information needed to solve a specific problem, can access this information efficiently and quickly; identify keywords and related terms to access information of interest; can identify different types and formats of potential information sources and do many more things

Media literacy is an integral part of media education. At the same time, its appearances are increasing. Although the concepts entering our language as a result of media analysis today, i.e. media literacy, media education, media study, etc., are related to each other, media is the reception, sorting, and analysis of information. , together with the concept of media literacy, the concepts of media education, media study, and media culture are used in the assessment.

For example: Media education

- media is integrated in the curriculum, subjects are studied on the basis of aro;
- that the "media topic" should be analyzed within a specific discipline;
- a critical approach to the media through practice and analysis;
- to study its form, technologies, methods of information transmission;
- to study media agencies, their social, political and cultural role;
- the student's communication with the mass media;
- research activities;
- studies the influence of the media on the audience through language and art.

Media studies in turn:

- theoretical study of media;
- comparative analysis of the media;
- its conceptual structure;
- analysis of media text and methods of its creation;
- interdependence of mass communication, cinematography and cultural sciences;
- He studies the influence of mass media.

Media literacy is the study of media and is based on the following outcomes of media education and aims to:

- understanding the impact of media on individuals and society;
- understanding of mass communication process;
- ability to understand and analyze media texts;
- understanding the media context;
- creating media texts and analyzing them;
- the media sets the tasks of evaluating texts and sorting them.

Today, the media, i.e., mass media, cinema, theater, types of art, cultural exchanges, any information transmitted through the Internet has a certain effect on the human mind and changes its worldview. is causing change. The main goal of the application of the above concepts and the pursuit of media education, media literacy, media criticism and media studies today is the creation of information, understanding the process of its dissemination, commercial, political, economic, spiritual and to be able to evaluate the information that is being disseminated for cultural purposes.

At the moment, the basics of media education should be included in the curriculum of every educational institution, the basics of media education should be explained to students and young people in the educational process in schools in the form of interactive, various games, and the growing generation should choose what is necessary in the intense flow of information. and allows him to be critically evaluated. This, in turn, serves as a basis for further strengthening of the citizenship position of young people in the future, to be able to objectively assess the events taking place in the world and make the right decisions. From the pedagogical point of view, multimedia tools are a new computer-based approach to the educational process of elementary school students. In this way, it is an important tool in increasing the level of efficiency of the educational process among students. For this reason, it is recommended to use "Multimedia lesson", "Slide lesson", "Seminar lesson", which represent the main aspects of the problem-solving and pedagogical technologies that develop in the study of elementary school lessons. A seminar lesson is a lesson that gathers independent performances of students and creates a basis for discussion when necessary. In such classes, the teacher acts as a guide, while students engage in learning activities as independent, creative individuals with their own opinions. The use of "multimedia lessons" allows to increase the quality and efficiency of the educational process. In this process, the teacher:

- Presents the educational material visually;
- Can quickly deliver new material;
- Can control the speed and volume of information with the help of animations.

CONCLUSION:

The main goal of teaching media literacy and information culture in Uzbekistan is to teach students today's modern media and information literacy, the culture of using the Internet and social networks, knowledge of information culture, psychological, regulatory, educational, ideological, information, consists in teaching the tasks of diagnosis and perspective setting. In addition, to ensure that students have the skills to analyze the main signs, components of the information culture of a person and pedagogical, social, technological, systematic, cultural, psychological, pedagogical, social approaches to understanding the phenomenon of information culture. Competence, media competence, dialogue, communication, the spread of fake news in the information space and the resulting problems, various threats, social and informational factors in the media space, study and improvement of the experience of countries that are leaders in the field of media education. Increasing the effectiveness of using media education in the continuous

education system in Uzbekistan, forming the network ethics of social media, that is, infoethics, media activities in Uzbekistan and abroad, including the activities of television, radio, the global network of the Internet, and the effectiveness of printed publications is to form the skills of making critical and comparative conclusions about the issues of improvement.

The development of information and communication technologies is changing the way people use mass media. Media literacy is increasingly important in today's society because media is primarily created and consumed online. Arming students with the skills necessary to be savvy consumers of information will help them develop strong digital citizens with the ability to evaluate resources and participate in safe and healthy digital conversations.

In today's globalization process, improving the knowledge and skills of young people in using modern information and communication networks, especially the Internet, and analyzing information is considered an important issue. In 2010, the monograph "Media Literacy and New Humanism" was published by the UNESCO Institute of Information Technologies in Education (IITE). The monograph is aimed at developing the conceptual basis of new educational programs for media and information literacy (MIL) for teachers. The process of developing media literacy in Uzbekistan in 2015 began to actively promote this topic among journalists, in particular, in higher educational institutions specializing in the training of journalist personnel. Based on the advanced world experience, the methodological foundations of the introduction of media literacy were developed. In particular, the training manual "Uzbekistan on the way to the development of media education" was prepared. It is worth noting that UNESCO projects made a great contribution to this process in Uzbekistan at the initial stage. In particular, starting from the 2021-2022 academic year in Uzbekistan, the "Media literacy" section was included in the "Education" textbook of 10-11th graders. Media literacy classes have been held in journalism faculties and departments of universities of the republic, such as Journalism and mass communication university of Uzbekistan, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, Uzbekistan National University, Uzbek State World Languages University, Karshi State University, Samarkand State Foreign Languages Institute from 2022-2023, it was included for the first time as a separate independent subject in the complex of humanities of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami. Today, the subject "Media Literacy and Information Culture" is taught as a compulsory subject in all educational areas of TSPU.

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